

BASIC DEFINITIONS OF TWELVE LAYER IOT ARCHITECTURE FOR SMART CITY

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Abstract. *The IoT architecture "Smart City" is considered, which provides a solution to the problems of municipal management of the urban economy on the basis of digital technologies. The actual needs of the urban economy are determined, the achievements in the field of digital data processing technologies that positively affect the urban economy are analyzed. The paper formulates the concept, architecture and principles of creating a new infocommunication education "Smart City". In this article, we will analyze the various classes of IoT solutions and their respective implementations. As a result, recommendations will be given on the steps to implement the IoT architecture and we will try to highlight the general trends of IoT solutions. We will also try to formulate the main problem areas, which should be considered when building the architectures of specific IoT solutions and possible problem areas of architectures.*

Keywords. *municipal government, urban economy, smart city, digital technologies, IoT, IoT Architecture, Performance, Simulation Model, Cloud, Edge, Mist, Fog Computing, Smart City, Query.*

INTRODUCTION

Since 1950, the number of people living in cities has risen almost six-fold to over 4 billion. That number is projected to increase by another 2.5 billion, by 2050. The smart city, coupled with the Internet of Things (IoT), is one of the most promising technologies to address the severe strain that this rapid population growth imposes on the public services and infrastructure of cities. A smart city uses Internet of Things (IoT) sensors in urban areas to collect data and automate systems such as traffic, energy use, and waste management. By doing so, smart cities improve the efficiency of urban services, reduce costs, and deliver a higher standard of living.

The Internet of Things is a fundamental column in the development of smart cities. With the help of IoT technologies, communities can improve energy distribution, reduce traffic congestion, simplify waste collection and improve air quality. Intelligent sensors are able to generate large volumes of data in real time, which are collected and duly used (through cloud computing) to manage public assets and optimize the provision of services.

IoT solutions are penetrating from one market to another and are not exclusive prerogatives. In each region, we can find all classes of IoT solutions. The main tasks are the management and regulation of car traffic, night / day street lighting, notification of danger to pedestrians, identification of non-standard and dangerous situations in the city.

IOT ARCHITECTURE

The figure below shows the layer architecture of IoT solutions. The IoT topology is different from the usual layer model such as OSI. This is not a linear and more complex flow graph. Some components are optional and may not be present in a particular solution class. Two

types of logic can be present - M2M (from car to car) and M2P (from car to person), as well as more special cases such as C2C (from car to car, usually in the same LTE mobile cell).

The IoT solution has two physical locations - the first is the end (peripheral) devices, and the second is in the Backend data center on servers or in the cloud. At the same time, this is not a classic client-server application architecture, as we will see below.

Picture 1. General architecture of the IoT solution for Smart City

Below we will analyze each layer separately and compare its features with the actual classes of IoT solutions .

1. Physical Layer. This level represents two types of operations - the collection of information (Sensors) and the implementation of mechanical work (Actuators).

Sensors can be divided into the following categories:

- Sensors:
- Light: Photo diodes/transistors/resistors, PIR detectors
- Sound: Microphones, ultrasonic sensors
- Switches, in particular limit switches, registering extreme points of mechanical movement. Rotation angle or rotation speed meters.

2. Edge Layer. This level is usually connected to one sensor or actuator. It provides the minimum functionality to convert analog information to digital and/or vice versa. For connection of sensors there are the same requirements for price and power consumption. Many manufacturers producing these types of devices do not have a uniform standard for data model, configuration, and operation, which creates separate integration problems.

To reduce power consumption, peripherals typically have four modes of operation:

- Sleeping mode

- The mode of measuring and collecting information from sensors
- Mode of communication, transmission and receipt of information
- Installation and connection mode

3. Local network Layer. Data transfer is the most energy-intensive part of the peripheral device, because most peripheral devices are not connected to the mains and wired communications. In addition, peripheral devices can be located quite far from the Gateway (within a few kilometers). On the other hand, the amount of information transmitted is usually quite small. The following protocols are used at the peripheral communication level:

- ZigBee / Zwave
- BLE
- lora
- Proprietary low band

4. Gateway Layer. in an IoT solution:

- If the Backend receives raw information, this will increase its power and the costs will be very high.
- Backend operation cannot guarantee real-time response for a large number of peripherals.
- Due to security restrictions, some information cannot be sent to the Backend and cannot be permanently monitored by a human. Such information includes data from street surveillance cameras, medical information, etc.

5. Wide network Layer. This layer separates the peripheral and BackEnd parts of the overall solution. The gateway is mostly connected to the BackEnd using mobile wireless such as 4G/5G, but sometimes wired internet is used. The external communication logical layer has a standardized protocol for IoT solutions called LwM2M. The LwM2M protocol was designed to access each peripheral, but since many peripheral vendors do not support LwM2M interfaces, a gateway device can solve this problem and create a wrapper to communicate with peripherals.

The external communication layer also contains communication services and ISO models within itself. It includes balancing and location services based on the DNS service, COAP transport protocol, DTLS encryption, and many other components that are beyond the scope of this article.

6. Security Layer. This layer provides AAA functions (Authentication , Authorization and Accounting - authentication, authorization and accounting) and encryption / decryption along with other services related to the Internet. All Clouds have their own security implementations, but functionally they are all built on the principle of roles and permissions. As noted in the paragraph above, this layer also acts as a terminator for an encrypted DTLS connection. The end user's connection to the Backend also has a security layer component.

7. Middleware Layer. This layer provides internal Cloud functionality for load balancing, message queuing, and streaming information. The components of this layer should be duplicated and scaled automatically. The layer is implemented mainly on the basis of microservices or PaaS from Cloud providers. This requirement stems from the paradigm of jumps and troughs in data volume. Automatic scaling reduces the cost of backend implementation. The actual implementation of the service may be different, but the general principle remains the same - to provide asynchronous message passing with buffering and load balancing. In this way, different components of the Backend can do their work independently and scale horizontally depending on the load. Below is a table of the each layer for IoT architecture of the Smart City (Table 1.)

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8. ETL layer. The internal ETL (Extract, Transform and Load) is the third ETL operation. The first was in the peripheral, the second was in the gateway. Back End ETL collects data from all peripherals and gateways and is responsible for the following operations:

- Collection of information
- Bringing information to a standard form
- Saving information for future use
- Information lifecycle management including archiving and destruction
- Notification of other services about the arrival of new data

Table 1.

Definitions of the layers for IoT architecture of the Smart City

No.	Layers	Layer types	Requirements
1.	Physical layer	Light and sound sensors. Video cameras. Pedestrian and vehicle sensors. Light control devices. Loudspeakers.	Low price
2.	Edge layer	SoC modules such as Raspberry Pi . Embedded machine intelligence systems.	Low price
3.	Local network layer	PLC, WiFi , BLE, LoRa .	Ad support Hoc , Mesh
4.	Gateway layer	Specialized computers with machine intelligence components.	backend support .
5.	Wide network layer	PLC, Ethernet, LTE, LvM2M, FOTA/SOTA.	LTE communication can use communication within the same cell without access to the Backend .
6.	Security layer	Mainly implemented in the Cloud . AWS has over 50% usage. AWS uses 2 core services: R53 and IAM. Also EC2 for DTLS termination .	Requires many different roles, vertical by department (police, administration, service, residence) and horizontal (position in the organization)
7.	Middleware layer	There is not much peak load data in this class. Streaming video and correlated	No special requests. A typical load balancer with a queuing

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		search for situational data are more important here.	mechanism. However, the implementation of streaming video using media servers is required.
8.	ETL Layer	RabbitMQ , MQTT, Kafka. Docker containers, Lambda/Function. SQL, NoSQL , Bucket storages .	Large amount of information. You need to pay attention to the design so as not to fall into excessive Cloud payments
9.	Big Data / Analytic Layer	Recognition of abnormal events. Disaster Prevention	No special requirements
10.	Notification layer	Notification via mobile app. Call in an emergency.	No special requirements
11.	Presentation layer	Warning pedestrians about the danger on the road. Emergency signals for police, ambulance and firefighters. Recommendations for drivers.	You need a single city WiFi Internet HotSpot and an application on your mobile.
12.	Configuration layer	Shadowing , twin pair , etc .	No special requirements

9. Big Data and Analytic Layer. Depends on the specific IoT application . Big data and the analytic layer will extract situational information from the entire set of peripherals. This part is less standardized because it differs greatly from one application to another due to the different tasks of the solutions. AI/ML algorithms are also widely used in this layer.

10. Notification layer. There can be multiple components at this level, but they all have a subscription notification algorithm. The client application subscribes to the necessary events and, when this happens, receives an informational signal - a notification. Mostly email applications and mobile clients, less phone calls (used for emergency alerts). The mobile app is forced to sleep to consume power, but iOS and Android have a notification mechanism to indicate the arrival of new data.

11. Presentation Layer. IoT application can have two flows: M2M (machine to machine) and M2P (machine to person). The presentation layer associated with the M2M stream, where Back End processes the information and provides it to the customer or support engineer. Today there is no standardized UI/UX representation for this level, but I hope to have one in the near future.

12. Configuration Layer. This layer applies to both M2M and M2P streams and acts as storage for three types of peripheral device statuses:

- Current state of the peripheral device

- The new state of the peripheral to be loaded.
- Intermediate Peripheral Status - Indicates the process of updating from old states to new ones. Often this status is absent.

CONCLUSION

In this paper we analyzed layers of the IoT architecture for Smart City. Summarizing the above. The following development trends are observed in IoT solutions:

- Sensors are divided into 2 groups:
- Simple, cheap, with the lowest possible energy consumption. Low speed and high range of information transmission. These are actually one-time devices that are not subject to maintenance.
- ETL processes take place at several levels - peripherals, gateways, and in the backend . While there is no single approach, what should be done at each level, but the ideology is that everything that can be processed should be processed at the lowest possible level.
- The main, universal means of information transmission is the wireless Internet. But the actual protocols differ at different levels. The logical level of communication is the LvM2M protocol.

I hope this article will be useful, at least for the first acquaintance with IoT projects. In the future, I will try to provide specific implementations of IoT solutions.

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